

Distributed processing of the attitude update through segmented spline calculations

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ABSTRACT. This note describes a method to distribute the attitude processing by dividing the attitude spline into overlapping segments. The method is useful when there are too few natural gaps in the data. An Appendix contains some useful conventions and explanations concerning splines and B-splines.

1 Introduction

In [4] a method for distributed processing of the attitude update was described, in which the different nodes contributed to the normal equations of the same spline function. The spline was then solved in a special process after adding the different components of the normal equations. The method was designed with a particular processing system in mind, in which the database holding the observations was distributed among the processing nodes according to position on sky, such that a particular node had the most efficient access to a subset of the observations.

The setup for the current AGIS is completely different. In order to process the attitude update in a distributed manner it is now more convenient to divide the data temporally. That is, we want to hand out the processing of different time segments to different nodes. The required temporal division of the data is natural and simple when data gaps (longer than a few seconds) are available at suitable intervals. However, even without gaps such a division can be introduced artificially and in a simple manner, without any significant loss of accuracy. This is described below. For reference purposes, conventions for notation and some important properties of splines and B-splines are explained in the Appendix.¹

2 Assignment of a regular knot sequence

We begin by noting the algorithm for assigning a regular knot sequence to a given time interval, for example between two data gaps. Let $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ be the time interval over which an attitude spline should be fitted (we shall refer to this as the ‘spline interval’, cf. Fig. 7). Moreover, let $M > 0$ be the order of the spline (e.g., $M = 4$ for a cubic spline) and N the number of degrees of freedom of the spline (i.e., the number of spline coefficients determining the spline). In practice we must have $N > M - 1$, and the whole

¹For better consistency with Java conventions, the present notation differs slightly from that in [3].

FIGURE 1: Definition of a regular knot sequence for fitting a cubic spline (order $M = 4$) in the interval $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$. The spline interval is divided into $N - 3$ knot intervals of equal length $\Delta t = (t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{beg}})/(N - 3)$. For the more general knot placement, see Fig. 7.

spline interval $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ is divided into $N - M + 1$ sub-intervals. The knot sequence is $\{\tau_k\}_{k=0}^{N+M-1}$, where

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{\text{beg}} \equiv \tau_0 = \tau_1 = \dots = \tau_{M-1} < \\
 \tau_M \leq \tau_{M+1} \leq \dots \leq \tau_{N-1} < \\
 \tau_N = \tau_{N+1} = \dots = \tau_{N+M-1} \equiv t_{\text{end}} \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

That is, the first and last M knots are placed at the endpoints of the time interval, and the remaining $N - M$ knots are placed in a non-decreasing sequence strictly interior to the spline interval. Interior knots may have up to M -fold multiplicity (i.e., up to M knots may be placed at the same t). At a knot of multiplicity m ($1 \leq m \leq M$), the spline and its first $M - m - 1$ derivatives are continuous. At a knot of multiplicity $m = M$, the spline itself is discontinuous.

By default, the interior knots will be equidistant and simple (of multiplicity 1), i.e.,

$$\tau_k = t_{\text{beg}} + (k - M + 1)\Delta t, \quad k = M \dots N - 1 \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta t = (t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{beg}})/(N - M + 1)$ is the (constant) knot interval.

The nominal situation for the AGIS attitude update is to use cubic splines ($M = 4$). Thus the spline interval begins and ends with 4-fold knots as illustrated in Fig. 1. The least-squares fitting determines the N coefficients $\{c_n\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$ in Eq. (3).

3 Choice of overlapping time intervals

In order to distribute the fitting of a single spline $S(t)$ (defined on the spline interval $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ by means of the knot sequence $\{\tau_n\}_{n=0}^{N+M-1}$) over several processors, we may divide the spline interval into smaller, but overlapping segments. Each segment is then fitted independently, and the adopted $S(t)$ is taken from the different segments by discarding redundant pieces.

This idea is simple, but three questions need to be addressed:

1. How much should the segments overlap?

FIGURE 2: The top diagram shows a cubic spline fitted to a Heaviside step function, using a regular knot sequence with knots at integer values of the abscissa. The bottom diagram shows the residuals of the fit on a logarithmic scale.

2. How should the knots be selected for each segment?
3. How can the segmented solutions be combined into a single spline?

How much should the segments overlap? The main reason why splines are so useful is that they are *local* in the sense that a change in the data at point t' has little effect on the fitted spline at t , provided that $|t' - t|$ is large enough, i.e., that there are enough knots between the two points. For a regular knot sequence the influence decreases exponentially with distance, as illustrated in Fig. 2. For a cubic spline the decay factor is asymptotically $\simeq 1.86$. Thus, after 12 or so knot intervals the influence is reduced by more than a factor

FIGURE 3: Illustrating the assignment of knots for the attitude update solutions in two consecutive segments K and $K + 1$, with a breakpoint at knot index x and using $2L$ overlapping knot intervals.

1000, which seems more than sufficient for an iterative updating of the spline coefficients.

Let us denote by L the number of knot intervals needed for efficient damping of end-effects, e.g., $L = 12$ for cubic splines. Then clearly the segments need to overlap by at least $2L$ knot intervals, so that one can discard half of the overlap in each segment, and still have accurate updates at the retained points.

How should the knots be selected for each segment? Suppose we have the knot sequence $\{\tau_n\}$ and want to break the calculations at the interior knot τ_x (where x is integer). The proposed solution is not to change the knot sequence, but only use a subset of them for each segment. This is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Thus, for segment K (which in the end will be valid up to τ_x) we choose $t_{\text{end}}(K) = \tau_{x+L}$ and add the subsequent $M - 1$ knots from the original sequence as posterior knots to the segment. The next segment $K + 1$ (which in the end will be valid from τ_x onwards) we choose $t_{\text{beg}}(K + 1) = \tau_{x-L}$ and add the preceding $M - 1$ knots from the original sequence as anterior knots to the segment. The segments are then processed independently. Note however that the same observations will be used by both segments in the overlap region.

How can the segmented solutions be combined into a single spline? Recall that the attitude process always computes an update to the current B-spline coefficients c_n of the spline function $S(t)$ covering the whole spline interval. With reference to Fig. 3, the solutions for the two segments K and $K + 1$ are the updates to the coefficients c_n for the relevant n . The index n refers to the B-spline with support $[\tau_n, \tau_{n+M-1}]$. That is, in segment K updates are computed for c_n up to and including $n = x + L - 1$, while in segment $K + 1$ updates are computed for c_n starting with $n = x - L - M + 1$. At least in the middle part of the overlap region, the updates for a given n should be essentially the same in the two segments. It therefore does not matter much which of the results is chosen. The mid-point is at index $n = x - M/2$ if M is even, or half-way between $x - (M + 1)/2$ and $x - (M - 1)/2$ if M is odd. We may agree to use the solution from segment K to update c_n up to an including index $n = x - M/2$ (using truncated integer division), while the solution from segment $K + 1$ is used starting with $n = x - M/2 + 1$. The important thing is that no n is missed by the updating, nor updated twice.

4 Other considerations

Once all the coefficients c_n for the whole spline interval have been updated from the different segmented solutions, the segmentation loses its meaning and can in principle be forgotten. For example, when evaluating the spline at a specific time t , it does not matter to which segment that instant belonged. In the next iteration of the attitude update, a different segmentation can in principle be selected.

The selection of anterior and posterior knots for the segments must be done from the knot sequence of the whole spline interval. This means that we cannot use the nice trick of putting these knots at the endpoints of the segment, as was done for the whole spline interval in Sect. 2, and which is numerically advantageous as explained in the Appendix. Only the anterior knots of the first segment and the posterior knots of the last segment are collapsed. However, the penalty in terms of a somewhat worse condition number is probably worth paying to avoid the nuisance of redefining knots for every segment.

The overlapping segments mean that a fraction of the observations need to be processed twice in the attitude updating. The fraction equals the ratio of the overlap length to the mean length of the segment, and increases the shorter the segments are made. Suppose that a segment covers just a single day (it would not seem reasonable to have even shorter segments). With a mean knot interval of $\Delta t = 15$ s and $L = 12$, the fractional overlap is only 0.4%, which should be acceptable.

Appendix: Notation and some properties of B-splines

A.1. Splines

A spline is piecewise polynomial function $S(t)$ defined on some interval $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$. That is, if the interval is divided into $K > 0$ sub-intervals by means of the instants t_k (called knots), such that $t_{\text{beg}} = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_K = t_{\text{end}}$, then in the sub-interval $t_k \leq t < t_{k+1}$ the spline function $S(t)$ equals some polynomial $P_k(t)$, $k = 0 \dots k - 1$. The splines of interest here consist of polynomials of some fixed order M (or degree $M - 1$); typically $M = 4$, corresponding to cubic splines. Moreover, the splines are usually maximally smooth, i.e., $S^{(m)}(t) = d^m/dt^m$ is continuous for $t_{\text{beg}} < t < t_{\text{end}}$ and $m = 0 \dots M - 2$.²

The K polynomials of order M require KM coefficients for their specification. For a maximally smooth spline, there are $M - 1$ continuity conditions for each interior knot, namely $S^{(m)}(t_k^-) = S^{(m)}(t_k^+)$ for $m = 0 \dots M - 2$ and $k = 1 \dots K - 1$; thus a total of $(K - 1)(M - 1)$ constraints. The spline consequently has $KM - (K - 1)(M - 1) = K + M - 1$ degrees of freedom.³ In the context of least-squares fitting, this equals the number of unknowns (parameters to fit), which we denote by N . In the following we take N and M to be the characteristic numbers of the spline, rather than K and M . For a maximally smooth spline we have $K = N - M + 1$.

²The 0th derivative is of course the function itself, $S^{(0)}(t) = S(t)$.

³When the spline is used for interpolation, it is typically chosen to go exactly through the $K + 1$ values $S(t_k)$ for $k = 0 \dots K$. This leaves $(K + M - 1) - (K + 1) = M - 2$ degrees of freedom. Thus, for a cubic spline ($M = 4$), two more conditions must be imposed for the spline to become unique. The most common choice is to make the second derivative vanish at t_{beg} and t_{end} . This defines the ‘natural’ interpolating spline. By contrast, when splines are least-squares fitted to data, as in the attitude determination problem, there are typically many data points per sub-interval, and no need for special endpoint conditions.

FIGURE 4: The first six B-splines of order $M = 4$ (cubic) defined on the regular knot sequence τ_0, τ_1, \dots . For better visibility, each B-spline is vertically displaced by one unit, and the non-zero parts are drawn in thick lines.

A.2. B-Splines

There are many different ways in which a spline could be represented (parameterized). The approach taken here is to consider $S(t)$ as a linear combination of some basis functions $B_n(t)$,

$$S(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} c_n B_n(t) \quad (3)$$

where c_n are coefficients to be determined. Choosing the basis functions to have minimal support (see below) for the given order and smoothness leads to the so-called B-splines [1].

The B-splines are uniquely defined by the adopted knot sequence. In the following we shall use τ_n (rather than t_n) to denote the knots associated with the B-splines. The reason is that the knot sequence for the B-splines has a slightly more general interpretation than just the simple division of $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ considered above. Moreover, when fitting the spline to given data points, this allows us to use t_k (for example) to denote the time associated with the k th data point, without ambiguity.

The knot sequence must be non-decreasing, $\tau_0 \leq \tau_1 \leq \tau_2 \leq \dots$, and at least two knots must be different. Very often we use a regular knot sequence in which $\tau_{n+1} = \tau_n + \Delta\tau$ for some $\Delta\tau > 0$ (the knot interval). Figure 4 shows the first six cubic B-splines defined on a regular knot sequence. Note that the non-zero part of each B-spline, shown in heavy line, stretches over M consecutive knot intervals. We use the convention that the B-splines are labelled with the same index as the left-most knot of its non-zero part; therefore, the support of $B_n(t)$ is (τ_n, τ_{n+M}) .

It is not possible to construct a maximally smooth spline function of order M that is non-zero over less than M consecutive knot intervals. This is what we mean by the statement that B-splines have minimal support: they could not be shortened without losing some smoothness. This is an important property for the least-squares fitting, as shown by the following consideration. Least-squares fitting of (3) to a given set of data points (t_k, z_k) (where $t_k \in [t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ for each k) will be done by forming normal equations. The normal equations matrix \mathbf{N} is a symmetric, positive definite matrix of dimension⁴ $N \times N$. Since N may be very large, it is desirable that the matrix is sparse, i.e., that most elements are zero. It is easy to see that element N_{ij} will be non-zero as soon as $B_i(t_k)B_j(t_k) \neq 0$ for some data point k . To make the matrix maximally sparse, we should therefore choose basis functions with minimal support. B-splines have minimal support and are therefore ideal for least-squares fitting using sparse matrix algebra.

Since the support of a B-spline of order M extends over at most M consecutive knot intervals, we have $N_{ij} = 0$ for $|i - j| > M - 1$. This shows that \mathbf{N} is a symmetric banded matrix with (half-) bandwidth equal to $M - 1$. Cholesky decomposition preserves the band structure of the matrix and is therefore ideal for solving the normals. (It is also numerically very efficient.)

A.3. Calculation of B-splines

At any given point t there are at most M non-zero B-splines, namely $B_{\ell-M+1}(t), B_{\ell-M+2}, \dots, B_{\ell}(t)$, where ℓ is the ‘left index’ of t , such that $\tau_{\ell} \leq t < \tau_{\ell+1}$. They can be computed simultaneously in a numerically stable way by means of de Boor’s algorithm [1], which in pseudo-code can be written:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l}
 \text{input: } t, \{\tau_n\}, \text{ and } \ell \text{ such that } \tau_{\ell} \leq t < \tau_{\ell+1} \\
 b_0 \leftarrow 1 \\
 \text{for } i = 0 \dots M - 2 \\
 \quad R_i \leftarrow \tau_{\ell+i+1} - t \\
 \quad L_i \leftarrow t - \tau_{\ell-i} \\
 \quad s \leftarrow 0 \\
 \quad \text{for } j = 0 \dots i \\
 \quad \quad u \leftarrow b_j / (R_j + L_{i-j}) \\
 \quad \quad b_j \leftarrow s + R_j \times u \\
 \quad \quad s \leftarrow L_{i-j} \times u \\
 \quad \text{next } j \\
 \quad b_{i+1} \leftarrow s \\
 \text{next } i \\
 \text{output: } \{b_0 \dots b_{M-1}\}
 \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

On output we have $b_0 = B_{\ell-M+1}(t), \dots, b_{M-1} = B_{\ell}(t)$. If needed, the derivatives of the B-splines with respect to t can be computed simultaneously with little additional effort.

⁴In the attitude determination problem, each of the four components of the quaternion is represented by a spline, so the number of parameters is actually $4N$ and the normal matrix is of dimension $4N \times 4N$. Alternatively, we may take the elements of \mathbf{N} to be sub-matrices of dimension 4×4 . The indices i and j used below refer to these sub-matrices.

FIGURE 5: B-splines of order $M = 4$ (cubic) on a knot sequence including a triple knot ($\tau_4 = \tau_5 = \tau_6$). The non-zero parts are drawn in thick lines.

By inspection of (4) it is found that the knots used for computing the B-spline values in the interval $[\tau_\ell, \tau_{\ell+1})$ are $\tau_{\ell-M+2}$ through $\tau_{\ell+M-1}$. For example, with reference to Fig. 4 (with $M = 4$), the B-splines between τ_3 and τ_4 (i.e., for left index $\ell = 3$) depend on $\{\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_6\}$, **but not on τ_0 or τ_7** , in spite of the fact that $B_0(t)$ in general depends on τ_0 and $B_3(t)$ depends on τ_7 .

A.4. Use of multiple knots

The algorithm (4) works also in the case when several consecutive knots are placed at the same t coordinate. Having a knot of multiplicity m (i.e., m knots at the same t) removes the continuity for derivatives of order $M - m$ and higher. The normal situation is that the knots have multiplicity 1, which means that the spline is continuous at the knots up to and including its $(M - 2)$ th derivative, but discontinuous in its $(M - 1)$ th derivative. By inserting multiple knots at some specific instant, one allows the spline to become less smooth at this point. For example, in a cubic spline ($M = 4$) a triple knot ($m = 3$) allows the first derivative to become discontinuous at that point, while leaving the spline function itself continuous. The corresponding set of B-splines (on an otherwise regular knot sequence) is shown in Fig. 5. In the Gaia attitude processing, multiple knots will be used for modelling the effects of micrometeoroid impacts.⁵

Multiple knots may also be used at the endpoints of the spline interval $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$. At any

⁵The impact causes an (almost) instantaneous change in angular velocity, corresponding to a discontinuity in the first derivative of the attitude spline. This can be achieved in a cubic spline by means of a triple knot. However, the angular acceleration (depending on the torques) may in principle be unchanged by the impact, and therefore we might want to have a spline function that is discontinuous in its first (and third and higher) derivatives, but continuous in its zeroth and second derivatives. Basis functions of this kind exist, but a general algorithm for their calculation, in the context of (4), has not been worked out.

FIGURE 6: B-splines of order $M = 4$ (cubic) on a knot sequence similar to the one in Fig. 4, except that the first three knots are shifted to coincide with the fourth knot, ($\tau_0 = \tau_1 = \tau_2 = \tau_3$). The non-zero parts are drawn in thick lines.

point in this interval, there must be exactly M non-zero B-splines in order that a linear combination of them should be able to represent an arbitrary spline of order M . Again, with reference to Fig. 4 (for $M = 4$), we see that this is the case to the right of τ_3 (or τ_{M-1} in general). Thus we should put $\tau_{M-1} = t_{\text{beg}}$. The first $M - 1$ knots can in principle be placed anywhere, as long as $\tau_0 \leq \tau_1 \leq \dots \leq \tau_{M-1}$: any such arrangement will produce M non-zero B-splines in the next sub-interval (τ_{M-1}, τ_M) , and although the B-splines are different depending on the arrangement of the knots, they are always linearly independent and therefore can be used as a basis for the spline. In particular, it is possible to put the M first knots at the same point, i.e., $\tau_0 = \tau_1 = \dots = \tau_{M-1} = t_{\text{beg}}$. Figure 6 shows what the cubic B-splines look like in this arrangement, for an otherwise regular knot sequence.

Corresponding considerations apply to the right limit of the spline interval: with N degrees of freedom, the support of the last B-spline $B_{N-1}(t)$ extends from τ_{N-1} to τ_{N+M-1} . The spline interval must end at $\tau_N = t_{\text{end}}$, and the remaining $M - 1$ knots can be placed anywhere provided that $\tau_N \leq \tau_{N+1} \leq \dots \leq \tau_{N+M-1}$. In particular, it is possible to have an M -fold knot at the endpoint of the spline interval, i.e., $t_{\text{end}} = \tau_N = \tau_{N+1} = \dots = \tau_{N+M-1}$. Figure 7 summarizes the placement of knots in relation to a given spline interval for given order M and degrees of freedom N (number of spline coefficients).

Although the placement of the first and last $M - 1$ knots is arbitrary, and does not change the resulting spline between t_{beg} and t_{end} , their placement does affect the numerical stability of the resulting least-squares system. Butkevich & Klioner [2] has pointed out that collapsing the anterior and posterior knots into the end knots (as in Fig. 6, so that $\tau_0 = \tau_1 = \dots = \tau_{M-1} = t_{\text{beg}}$ and $t_{\text{end}} = \tau_N = \tau_{N+1} = \dots = \tau_{N+M-1}$) results in a system with much smaller condition number than a regular sequence (as in Fig. 4). The reason for this can be readily understood from an inspection of Figs. 4 and 6.

FIGURE 7: Illustration of the knot placement for a spline of order M (e.g., $M = 4$ for a cubic spline) with N degrees of freedom. $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ is the spline interval over which the spline is fitted to given data points. The end knots τ_{M-1} and τ_N are placed at the endpoints of the spline interval. The $N - M$ interior knots are chosen to give the spline the desired flexibility, including multiple knots where required. The placement of the anterior ($\tau \leq t_{\text{beg}}$) and posterior knots ($\tau \geq t_{\text{end}}$) is in principle arbitrary: it does not change the fitted spline in $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$, but may affect the condition number of the least-squares system. The parameters of the fitted spline are the coefficients c_0, \dots, c_{N-1} of the B-splines $B_0(t)$ through $B_{N-1}(t)$.

References

- [1] de Boor C., 1978: *A Practical Guide to Splines*, Springer-Verlag, New York
- [2] Butkevich A.G., Klioner S.A., 2007: *Some statistical properties of various versions of the velocity determination from astrometric data*, GAIA-CA-TN-LO-AGB-003-1 (12 March 2007)
- [3] Lindgren L., 2001: *Proposed prototype processes for the GAIA Global Iterative Solution*, SAG-LL-034.2 (v. 2, 9 March 2001)
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Acronyms

The following table has been generated from the on-line Gaia acronym list:

Acronym	Description
AGIS	Astrometric Global Iterative Solution